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ASSESSMENT OF THE IMPACT OF HVDC SYSTEMS ON POWER SYSTEM RESTORATION

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Abstract

This research investigates the role that High-Voltage Direct Current (HVDC) technology could play in power system restoration. Typically, the need of system restoration occurs following extreme events that lead to a blackout of a power system. In such cases, it is important to restore the system load as fast as possible. System operators mainly procure black-start services from conventional generating units, that progressively energise the transmission network, build a skeleton from their terminals to other generating units and, eventually, the load. This energisation is subject to several network and ramp-up constraints of the generating units. Past studies have formulated the restoration of the system as an optimisation problem that aims to minimise the load supply interruption. This work extends on the existing framework, by integrating HVDC systems into the formulation and applying it to support the restoration, either through transfer of power or by using the converters as black-start units. The proposed formulation accommodates various HVDC configurations that can arise. Simulation results on the IEEE 39-bus system reveal that significant benefits can be obtained by the utilisation of HVDC links during black-start.

1. Introduction

After a power system black-out, it is essential to restore the power system in a fast and effective way in order to minimise the negative impact on the customers. The restoration itself is a complex procedure in which an optimal sequence of the network energisation path needs to be defined to interlink black start energy sources to the other units (providing the required cranking power) in order to re-energise the remaining network and restore the connected load.

Reference [1] uses the so-called “resilience trapezoid” to describe the different stages that a system undergoes following extreme events. These three stages are the disturbance progress, the post-disturbance degraded state and the system restoration state. Typically, the restoration phase takes much more time compared to the other states. Hence, to fully assess the operational resilience of a system, it is important to adequately analyse its performance during the restoration phase, especially if the Energy Non Served (ENS) is adopted as the main key performance indicator.

It is generally well documented that HVDC systems can improve power system restoration. In [7], a review of HVDC technologies and their benefits and drawbacks in the context of black start restoration is carried out. The current state of use of HVDC technologies in restoration is discussed and also the interest of applying Voltage Source Converters (VSC) in black start restoration is addressed from a theoretical point of view. However, in order to assess their overall impact on the system restoration, it is necessary to develop proper methods and tools, which to the authors’ knowledge, have not yet been documented in the literature.

This paper builds upon existing work in the literature by not only considering the restoration of AC networks with conventional means, but also assessing the capability, application and overall impact on the resilience metrics (i.e., ENS) of applying HVDC systems within the restoration procedure.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses the existing work in the literature, Section 3 describes the methodology followed in this work in order to integrate HVDC links in the restoration formulation. The added value and improvements in the restoration brought by HVDC are then demonstrated using various test cases in Section 4 and Section 5. Conclusions and possible future extensions are offered in Section 6.

2. Literature review

The process of power system restoration can be approached in several ways. On one hand, approaches based on heuristic methods exist and are mainly derived from the system operator experience. This approach is exemplified by [2], that proposes a three-stage power system restoration methodology integrating renewable energy sources. The aim is to identify a sequence of steps within the restoration procedure.

On the other hand, it is possible to formulate the restoration process as the result of an optimisation problem. However, this approach often involves complex, non-linear mathematical formulations, including the AC power flow equations and network constraints. To achieve a computationally tractable problem, linear approximations are typically adopted to reduce the problem formulation to a more tractable Mixed Integer

Linear Programming (MILP) formulation. Such approaches are documented in [3] and [4].

A MILP formulation of the restoration process that focuses solely on the topological path and branch energisation time is presented [3]. This approach provides a simplified model of the restoration process, making it computationally efficient, however it does not consider power transmission constraints or how the power transfer is distributed throughout the grid based on the Kirchhoff laws. The work presented in [4] extends on this by adding the geographical distance between different assets in the network to the MILP formulation. This allows to include certain technical constraints related to the starting of generators in the formulation, however, the electrical characteristics of the network are still not considered. As a result, infeasible restoration sequences can arise from such a formulation.

In [5] and [6], a linearisation of the Kirchhoff laws are integrated into the problem formulation to reduce the risk of obtaining an optimal restoration sequence that is not feasible in practice. This approach brings the mathematical model closer to the physical reality of power system operation, thereby increasing the likelihood of obtaining a viable and feasible solution. However, HVDC links were not considered.

In summary, the literature presents a variety of approaches to power system restoration, each with its own strengths and limitations. These approaches range from heuristic methods, optimisation-based approaches that offer computationally efficient models, to physically-informed methods that aim to produce feasible and practical solutions. However, to the authors' knowledge, existing literature has not considered the integration of HVDC equipment inside these formulations. This topic is covered by this work which aims to provide a modelling of VSCs in a MILP formulation, in order to assess their impact on power system restoration.

3. Methodology

3.1. Optimisation problem formulation

As discussed in the literature review, different approaches can be taken to deal with power system restoration. This study follows the same approach as in [4]. It focuses on evaluating the restoration using a MILP formulation, integrating a model of the AC network and of the HVDC equipment. The subsequent subsections define the main constraints related either to network operational requirements or physical constraints of the system. In addition to these constraints, the control variables and the objective of the problem are defined.

In a restoration problem, the aim is to re-energize the network and restore the loads of the system as quickly as possible. This main objective can be expressed as an optimisation problem minimising the non-supplied load over the considered time horizon. It is written as follows:

$$\min \sum_{i=1}^T \sum_{\ell \in \mathcal{L}} (P_{target,\ell,i} - P_{\ell,i}) \quad (1)$$

where $P_{target,\ell,i}$ is the nominal power consumption of load ℓ at time step i , and $P_{\ell,i}$ is the power of the load supplied at time

step i . T is the horizon of the optimization, and has been split in several discrete time steps, $i = 1, 2, \dots, T$.

To achieve an optimal (i.e. quick) restoration of the loads, the optimization will identify a sequence of actions defined by the following control variables:

- Status of branches, buses, and generators
- Active and reactive power of generators
- Status and reactive power of shunt reactors
- Active power consumption of loads

3.2. Constraints

3.2.1. Power system modelling

Before integrating the representation of the HVDC equipment, it is essential to develop a model for restoring the AC network. References [5] and [6] incorporate the most important physical constraints, based on the Kirchhoff laws. Implementing the non-linear Kirchhoff equations would significantly increase the complexity of the problem. Here the approach proposed in [5] for AC modelling is adopted, as it represents an adequate compromise between physical accuracy and computational burden.

The following constraints are imposed to obtain an adequate representation of the power flows and to ensure that the main system variables remain within their operational limits:

- Power balance between generation and load;
- Linearised Kirchhoff laws for active and reactive power, see (2)-(3);
- Voltage must remain within pre-defined limits;
- The flow through a line must respect the line rating;
- Generator active power output must remain below the maximum machine capability P_{max} . Ramp-up and cranking power constraints must also be respected. The reader is referred to [3]-[4] for a more detailed representation of these constraints.

In addition, as also discussed in [4], the network reactive power absorption capability is often a limiting factor during the first steps of the restoration. Just after their energisation, the lines are lightly loaded, which leads to non-negligible reactive power injection. Therefore, additional inequality constraints have to be included controlling the reactive power balance at each bus, as presented in [5]. This inequality constraint, as given by (4), intends to ensure that the network can absorb the reactive power at each step of the restoration.

However, depending on the location of the BS generators in the system, their reactive power capability can be insufficient and, can therefore be the limiting component during the first steps of the restoration. To overcome this limiting factor, shunt reactors may be necessary to speed up the restoration or even get it started. It is considered that this equipment is part of a network and has been adequately located by the system operator. Ideally, they should be located on the energisation path as they are mainly used at the beginning of the restoration when the reactive power production is high and as such can be deactivated later when they are not necessary anymore.

$$P_{i,j} = b_{i,j} \times (\theta_j - \theta_i) \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{i,j} = b_{i,j} \times (v_j - v_i) + g_{i,j} \times (\theta_j - \theta_i) \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_j Q_{i,j} + \sum_g Q_{min,g,i} + \sum_{sh} Q_{sh,i} + \sum_j B_{sh,i,j} \leq Q_{\ell,i}, \forall i \in \mathcal{B} \quad (4)$$

In (2) and (3), $b_{i,j}$ and $g_{i,j}$ respectively denote the conductance and susceptance of the line from bus i to j while $P_{i,j}$ and $Q_{i,j}$ are the active and reactive flows on the branch from bus i to j . In equation (4), $Q_{min,g,i}$ denotes the minimum reactive power of the generation at bus i , $Q_{sh,i}$ the reactive power of the shunt reactor at bus i , $B_{sh,i,j}$ the shunt capacitance of the branch from bus i to j and $Q_{\ell,i}$ the reactive power of the load at bus i . v_i and θ_i are the voltage module and angle at bus i .

Beyond the network equations, additional constraints are set regarding the energisation process. These rules apply to buses, branches and generators status. It is assumed that once energised, buses, branches and generators remain energised (5)-(7). Furthermore, the model ensures that the generator ramp-up constraints are respected and the restored load is monotonic at all nodes, see also (8).

$$\mathcal{S}_{n,i+1} \geq \mathcal{S}_{n,i}, \forall i \in T \quad (5)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_{g,i+1} \geq \mathcal{S}_{g,i}, \forall i \in T \quad (6)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_{b,i+1} \geq \mathcal{S}_{b,i}, \forall i \in T \quad (7)$$

$$P_{\ell,i+1} \geq P_{\ell,i}, \forall i \in T \quad (8)$$

In the following equations, n denotes nodes/buses, b denotes branches/lines, g for generators and ℓ for loads. \mathcal{S} denotes the status of the equipment: 0 means non energized and 1 means energized. T is the set of time steps.

It should be noted that the restoration process is considered to start after the energisation of the BS units. The first time step is just after energisation of the BS units and associated buses.

Finally some constraints are defined to control asset energisation. These constraints state that:

- A bus (without a BS unit) can be energised only after one of its adjacent branches is energised;
- A branch can be energised only after one of its buses is energised;
- An NBS generator can be energised only if its connection bus is also energised.

3.2.2. HVDC modelling

As far as the HVDC model is concerned, this work makes some simplifications to integrate them in the overall formulation: (i) the losses in the DC grid and converters are neglected, which is in line with the AC system modelling. (ii) the VSCs are represented as equivalent generators. The following active power balance (9) applies for all VSCs belonging to the same HVDC grid, \mathcal{G}_{DC} :

$$\sum_{vsc \in \mathcal{G}_{DC}} P_{vsc} = 0 \quad (9)$$

Furthermore, it is stated that a VSC can exchange power with its DC grid only if it is energised. The energisation status of each VSC is added to the set of variables presented in Section 3.1. The energisation rules of a VSC are the following:

- VSC can be energised if its AC connection node is energised (AC-side energisation);
- VSC can be energised if another VSC of the same DC grid is energised (DC-side energisation).

It is worth mentioning that two types of converters are considered which will impact the actions the VSC can take.

1. **Black-start VSC (BS VSC):** this VSC has black start capabilities, i.e. if it is energised (by the DC grid), it can energise its AC bus.
2. **Non-black-start VSC (NBS VSC):** it cannot energise its AC bus. Its AC bus must be energised throughout the energisation of the AC network.

The model presented in this section supports the following HVDC configurations:

- **Embedded point-to-point HVDC link:** the HVDC link connects two buses, belonging to the same synchronous grid.
- **Asynchronous point-to-point connection to an external system:** the external AC system can be modelled either as an equivalent black-start generator if there is an agreement between the two systems to provide black-start support or an NBS generator, if there is no such agreement or capability in place (e.g. if the external system represents an offshore wind farm).
- **Multi-terminal HVDC system,** which could be fully embedded, asynchronous, or a mix of the two.

Finally, it should be noted that several DC grids can be modelled within one network.

Figure 1: IEEE 39-bus system with additional VSCs used to test and evaluated benefits of the HVDC technology during a restoration process for (a) test case 1; (b) test case 2; and (c) test case 3.

4. Use case and results

4.1. Case studies

To test and evaluate the possible benefits brought by HVDC technology in the network, the IEEE 39-bus system is used as a starting point (see Fig. 1) [8]. In this case, the only black start unit is located at bus 30.

For the first test case, an additional embedded point-to-point HVDC interconnection has been added to the network, which is represented by a dashed red line in Figure 1 (a). The HVDC link is chosen such that it connects two electrically distant buses, one of which is close to the black start generator (bus 2) and the other close to one of the biggest load centres of the network (bus 20).

As mentioned in Section 3.2, the VSCs are represented as two equivalent generators linked with the DC power balance constraint (9). For this case, the VSCs have each a maximum active power capacity of 600 MW. The generator parameters, are provided in Table 1 and are the same for all test cases.

Table 1: Generators parameters.

Bus	Pmax [MW]	Qmin [MVar]	Aux. load [MW]	Ramp-up [MW/min]
B30	350	-158	0	5.5
B31	650	-293	8	4.1
B32	632	-284	7	3.9
B33	508	-229	5	3.3
B34	650	-293	8	4.1
B35	560	-252	5	3.6
B36	250	-113	6	3.5
B37	830	-374	13	5.8
B38	1000	-450	15	6.4
B39	573	-400	15	3.6

The second test case intends to demonstrate the benefits of an HVDC connection to an asynchronous network. Here it is assumed that the asynchronous network has not suffered a

black-out, hence it is modelled as an equivalent (already energized) generator. The HVDC link is connected at bus 24 through a BS VSC and consists also of a 600 MW link. The configuration is shown in Figure 1 (b).

The third test case consists of a multi-terminal DC grid. For this configuration, a DC grid made of three VSCs is considered. One of the VSC connects an asynchronous system to the main system. The two others VSCs are connected to bus 2 and bus 20, similarly to the first test case. This configuration is shown in Figure 1 (c).

An energisation time of 5 minutes is considered for buses and branches. It corresponds to the necessary time to energise the equipment once it can get energised by one of its adjacent components.

4.2. Results and discussion

Test case 1: To assess the advantages of HVDC and compare the benefits of BS VSC vs NBS VSC, three different configurations are first tested: (i) without energising the HVDC link, (ii) both converters are NBS VSC, (iii) the VSC at bus 20 has BS capability. Figure 2 shows the load restored over time for the tested configurations.

Figure 2: Comparison of the load restored over time with BS and NBS VSC.

The case with an NBS VSC provides the same results as without the DC line, hence the latter is not shown in Figure 2. The situation with a BS VSC has a positive impact on the load restoration speed. This can be evaluated thanks to ENS which is 9% lower in the case with a BS VSC (131 GWh instead of 144 GWh without BS VSC). Figure 3 shows the power through the VSC at bus 20.

Figure 3: VSC power with BS and NBS VSC for test case 1.

Figure 4 shows the energisation sequence of test case 1 with a BS VSC. Blue elements are energised early while red are energised later. Note that the optimization did not lead to energization of all elements (e.g., bus B11 and the connected lines were not energized).

Figure 4: Restoration sequence of buses and lines for test case 1 with BS VSC.

Test case 2: Figure 5 (a) compares the restoration speed between test case 1 with BS VSC and test case 2. The restoration is much faster for test case 2 thanks to the connection to an asynchronous system. Even if the two test cases are not comparable as the system topology is different, it shows that connecting to asynchronous networks with HVDC links can be very useful during a restoration, as it allows the network to be restored from several locations. This assumes that the DC connection and the external system are available immediately and they have not been impacted by the blackout,

too. An additional 9% reduction in ENS is observed compared to test case 1 with BS VSC.

In Figure 5 (b), the power going through VSC at bus 20 is compared between test case 1 and 2. There is a significant difference in the way the VSC is used. In test case 2, the use of the VSC at bus 20 is more intense in the first half of the restoration than in test case 1. This is explained by the additional connection to the asynchronous network that is available to supply part of the network, and therefore more power is available initially to supply the area close to bus 20.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Comparison of the (a) load restored and (b) the power through VSC at bus 20 with and without a DC connection to an asynchronous AC network.

Test case 3: This test case represents a three-terminal HVDC grid. For test case 3, ENS is 114 GWh, which represents a 14% improvement compared with test case 1 with BS VSC. The power exchanged on the three VSCs is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: VSC powers in test case 3.

5. Performance of the model

The optimisation model has been developed with GAMS and is solved using the CPLEX solver in single-thread mode on a processor Intel Core 7 11th Gen (1185G7 @3.00GHz). A relative tolerance on the optimal solution of 0.1% is used.

The solving time depends on the system topology, the BS location, on the shunts' location and size. It is generally below 10 minutes even if the topology can significantly impact the solving time. This is the case for multi-terminal test case where the computation time is much lower than a simple point-to-point configuration. The execution times for the presented cases are summarised in Table 2. These times are reasonable for offline analysis purposes as they are lower than 10 minutes.

Table 2: Performance of the test cases

Case	Description	Execution time [min]	ENS [GWh]
1	No HVDC	0:39	144
1a	With HVDC (NBS VSC)	2:53	144
1b	With HVDC and BS VSC at bus 20	6:44	132
2	With HVDC (BS) to async. system	7:27	118
3	Multi-terminal HVDC and BS VSCs	0:46	114

6. Conclusion and future work

This study investigates the application and benefits of HVDC technology for power grid restoration applying a MILP formulation of the network using linearised AC equations. The tests conducted on the IEEE 39-bus system demonstrate that BS VSCs substantially enhance load restoration after a blackout. The optimal placement of the DC line and BS assets remains of course crucial to fully leverage HVDC technology. By strategically locating these assets, power system operators can improve the speed and efficiency of grid restoration, minimising the time to restore the full system load. The tests also assess the benefit of connecting two asynchronous systems via an HVDC link from a restoration point of view. The system that is not affected by the blackout can immediately take part in restoring the affected system.

During the long-term planning of a grid, this model can provide valuable insights on the impact of an HVDC project on the restoration time (and consequently the resilience) of a power system after a blackout. For example, all other things being equal, the impact on restoration time could be the differentiating factor when deciding the landing point of an HVDC link. Alternatively, it could give an indication of the usefulness of procuring black-start service from an HVDC system.

Looking ahead, further research will involve testing the restoration tool under various grid configurations. Comparing the advantages of different setups that will help identify the most effective approach. A better profiling of the tool to

identify how the model and optimisation parameters impact the solution and execution time will also be performed. Additionally, validation of the restoration procedure through AC power flow computations will ensure compliance with physical network constraints. This work contributes therefore to the ongoing efforts to enhance power grid resilience and reliability in the face of disruptions and blackouts through the use of HVDC systems.

7. Acknowledgements

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